

Two new records of *Laciniaria plicata* (Draparnaud, 1801) from western Bohemia (Gastropoda: Clausiliidae)

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Two new records of *Laciniaria plicata* (Draparnaud, 1801) from western Bohemia are presented. All previous records are summarised and the distribution in western Bohemia is briefly discussed.

Key words: distribution, Czech Republic, Clausiliidae, new records

Introduction

Laciniaria plicata (Draparnaud, 1801) is a central European species, relatively common in eastern, and north-eastern Bohemia, whilst rare in western half of the country (LOŽEK 1956). HORSÁK et al. (2013) mentioned this species to be missing in Central and Western Bohemia, but several sites are known; see chapters Published data and New records. In the Czech Republic, this species prefers shaded rocks and ruins (LOŽEK 1956).

Published data

FLASAR (1998) summarised the data on the distribution of Gastropoda in northwestern Bohemia. The castle ruin Hauenstein near Krásný Les (5644) has been reported as the only site of *Laciniaria plicata* in western Bohemia (Karlovy Vary region). Few other sites of this species (Hasištejn near Místo (5545), Reisenburg near Osek (5348), Stropník near Osek (5348), Touchovice (5648), and Raná (5548)) are located close to western Bohemia, but belong to the Ústí nad Labem region.

The five sites in the northwestern Bohemian Forest (i.e. Šumava Mts) (Plzeň region) close to settlements Pajrek (6744) and Svatá Kateřina (6744) were published by HLAVÁČ (1998) and HLAVÁČ & HORSÁK (2000, 2002). The last records of *Laciniaria plicata* from western Bohemia, found in greenhouses in Sušice (6747), were published by DVOŘÁK in HORSÁK et al. (2004).

New records

Kraslice (5641), 50°19'24.872"N, 12°31'8.547"E, a ruderal site with stones in the Pod Nemocnicí street, 19 Apr 2016. Sušice (6747), 49°13'37.064"N, 13°31'25.744"E, greenhouses of the Studio Garden gardening, 26 Jun 2003; surroundings of the gardening, 26 Jun 2003.

Fig. 1. Present known distribution of *Laciniaria plicata* in western Bohemia and adjacent regions. New records are colored in red.

Discussion and conclusions

Laciniaria plicata is a very rare species in western Bohemia (Fig. 1). The new record from Kraslice is relatively near to the more or less continuous occurrence on the

border of Karlovy Vary and Ústí nad Labem regions (see FLASAR 1998). The published data from southernmost part of the Plzeň region (HLAVÁČ (1998) and HLAVÁČ & HORSÁK (2000, 2002)) are isolated as well as the new record from Sušice, where *L. plicata* is spreading to the outdoor from the greenhouses (DVOŘÁK in HORSÁK et al. 2004). No record is known from south Bohemia close to the Plzeň region (L. DVOŘÁK, unpubl. data).

References

- FLASAR I., 1998: Die Gastropoden Nordwestböhmens und ihre Verbreitung. – *Heldia, Münchner malakologische Mitteilungen*, München, 3(4): 1–210.
- HLAVÁČ J., 1998: Měkkýši (Mollusca) hradní zříceniny Pajrek u Nýrska a jeho okolí (Šumava) [Molluscs (Mollusca) of the castle ruin Pajrek near Nýrsko and its surroundings (Šumava Mts.)]. – *Silva Gabreta*, 2: 221–232 (in Czech).
- HLAVÁČ J. & HORSÁK M., 2000: Nový výskyt plzáka *Arion intermedius* Normand, 1852 (Pulmonata: Arionidae) v CHKO Šumava (Západní Čechy) [The slug *Arion intermedius* Normand, 1852 (Pulmonata: Arionidae) – new find in the Šumava Protected Landscape Area (Western Bohemia)]. – *Silva Gabreta*, 5: 113–120 (in Czech).
- HLAVÁČ J. Č. & HORSÁK M., 2002: Rozšíření plžů *Macrogastra badia* a *Laciniaria plicata* (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Clausiliidae) na Šumavě [Distribution of the snails *Macrogastra badia* and *Laciniaria plicata* (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Clausiliidae) in the Bohemian Forest]. – *Silva Gabreta*, 8: 191–204 (in Czech).
- HORSÁK M., DVOŘÁK L. & JUŘIČKOVÁ L., 2004: Greenhouse gastropods of the Czech Republic: current stage of research. – *Malacological Newsletter*, 22: 141–147.
- HORSÁK M., JUŘIČKOVÁ L. & PICKA J., 2013: Měkkýši České a Slovenské republiky. Molluscs of the Czech and Slovak Republics. – Kabourek, Zlín, 264 pp. (in Czech and English).
- LOŽEK V., 1956: Klíč československých měkkýšů [Key to the Mollusca of Czechoslovakia]. – *Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava*, 437 pp. (in Czech).